

HISTOLOGY – history, short review of techniques and application in modern science

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Abstract

Histology is a field of science focused on analysis of structure, development and function of cells and tissues of animals and plants. The study uses microscopy as its main tool of analysis. Histology includes the knowledge about microscopic structure of organs and also cytology and embryology. The science focused on histology of ill tissues and cells is called histopathology. It is a very important tool in analysis of anatomical pathology of morbid tissues, which appears in cancerous cells in animal or human body. Histology is essential for understanding and development of disciplines such as medicine, biology, veterinary medicine and many different sub-disciplines.

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The science of histology has a beginning in 17th century, when Marcello Malpighi invented and constructed one of the first microscopes, which could be used for studying very small biological particles, invisible to human eye. The constructor used his invention for analysis of organs and parts of animals such as bats and frogs. The analysis allowed him to discover the structure of the smallest blood vessels, which connect veins with arteries and are called capillaries.[1]

In the 19th century the histology was a separate academic discipline. The anatomist and pathologist Marie François Xavier Bichat is recognized as the creator of this field of science. The scientist used the term „tissue” for the first time and classified tissues into different categories, based on microscopic observations and analysis. The term „histology” appeared in 1819 and comes from two Greek words: *histos*, meaning „tissue”, and *logos* which stand for suffix- logia. In 1906 the Nobel Prize was given to two histologists: Camilio Golgi for invention of tissue staining method and Santiago Roman y Cajal for his theory of neural structure of the brain. The 20th century was the time of large progress in histology and resulted in its use and importance in other fields of science, especially for medicine and biology.[2,3]

Histology is a scientific study of animal or plant tissues which are sliced, stained with specific staining techniques. After slicing, the sections are analysed under a light microscope or an electron microscope. Multiple kinds of stains are usually used to make an easy distinction between different kinds of

tissues during the staining process. The tissues obtain various colours which makes the observation clearer and more precise.[4]

There are four basic types of tissues: muscle tissue, nervous tissue, connective tissue and epithelial tissue. Each of them has its own structure and function; also signs of pathological changes are different between tissues or even subtypes of tissues. [5]

Microscopy is the most important tool of histology. It is a technical field of theory, structure and usage of microscopes. In histology the most popular is light microscope and electron microscope. These devices allow cells and tissues observations, which are impossible to see with bare eye. [6]

The light microscope and its subtypes– phase-contrast microscope, fluorescent microscope, interference microscope or polarized microscope– with electronic microscope, are most often used during histological research. In light microscope the image of tissue structure is obtained by enlargement, which is possible due to integrated optical system. The light used in this kind of microscope is in visible spectrum and is called visible light. In comparison, the electron microscope uses a beam of accelerated electrons for magnifications of tissue. The electrons are moving in electric field, which makes them the source of illumination. [7]

The histological procedures start with isolation of material. The tissue can be isolated during biopsy, an operation or *post mortem*. Next, the tissue is preserved. The sections are put in a fixative, like ethanol or formaldehyde. Preservation in this case is a

very important procedure; it protects the tissue from rotting and degradation, caused by its own active enzymes. [8]

After isolation the slices of tissues have to be prepared for dyeing procedures. The preserved piece of tissue is very sensitive and fragile, which makes further manipulation impossible. Therefore, a tissue is put into the paraffin, which penetrates it and gives needed consistency for light microscopy. For electron microscopy, a tissue is soaked in epoxy resin. Because the materials used for embedding are not soluble in water, the biological material has to be dehydrated before embedding in paraffin or epoxy resin. The dehydration is preceded with baths of sample in higher concentrations of alcohol. This process removes the water from the tissue, which makes the penetration of embedding material more effective. After the embedding, the tissues are formed into blocks and sliced down on microtomes, the machine used to cut very slim slices of biological material. After sectioning the paraffin is removed from slices. If the epoxy resin was used for embedding, it remains and forms the sections. The procedure of section preparation takes up to 2 or 3 days. [9]

The alternative method of preparation of sections is the frozen section procedure. It is a fast way to fix histological sections, for example during the surgical operations. It is the alternative for paraffin method. The sections of tissue are refrigerated with the use of cryostat and sliced down on built-in microtome. This method provides the sections with lower quality, but at the same time it is very fast and preserves the lipids in tissues, which are extracted during the paraffin method with alcohol. [10]

In case of singular cells which come from cell culture, they can be observed under the microscope without embedding. The cells were observed *in toto*, as whole cells. They can be isolated from the surface of skin, mucous membranes or excretion. [11]

After the preparation, a tissue is dyed to ease the identification of its specific structures. The elements of cells and tissue have similar ability of light absorption. Under the microscope the diversity of tissue structure cannot be observed. The diversity is shown by the usage of staining techniques. The procedure can be based on three different mechanisms. In the first one the staining factor is binding with tissue elements. In the second, the binding factor is adsorbed to the surface of the elements. In the last one the chemical reaction is preceded, which makes certain structures of interest visible under the microscope. The staining procedures are described by histochemistry or immunohistochemistry, which is used to formulate the mechanisms of staining. [12]

The sections observed under the light microscope are usually stained with haematoxylin and eosin, which form H&E stain. Haematoxylin stains

the nuclei blue due to its affinity to nucleic acids localized in the cell nucleus. On the other hand, eosin stains the cytoplasm pink, because of its acidic properties. In case of electron microscopy, uranyl acetate and lead citrate are commonly used to impart contrast to the tissue. [13]

For several years the use of antigens has become a popular technique of protein, carbohydrates and lipids identification in tissue. This process is called immunochemistry or immunofluorescence, if the stain has fluorescent properties. The antibodies are identified by cell antigens; they bind with each other, which allows the identification of stained component through stain specific method of detection. Visualisation of antigen-antibody complex can be accomplished by the usage of enzymatic reaction. The antibody is conjugated to an enzyme, which provides the coloured product of reaction. [13]

In immunofluorescence the antibodies can be tagged by fluorophore, such as fluorescein or rhodamine. The visualisation of identified antigen in cell components is possible through the observation under fluorescence microscope. [14]

Histological techniques change size, shape and chemical composition of tissue elements. They are replaced and mechanically mutilated. Water solutions can elute some substances from a tissue, same as for organic solvents. The chemical mutilation during slicing on microtome and after, when the sections are straightened, result in visible changes in appearance of sections. All changes seen in sections of tissue are called artefacts. [15]

The interpretation of sections is quite problematic and demands specific abilities from the researcher. The structures of tissues are three-dimensional. The sections made from tissues are practically two-dimensional. To provide a correct interpretation of the given section, the spatial imagination is essential. The difficulties arise from natural localisation of tissue elements in its structure and their relative position. The process of slicing under different angles results in obtaining sections with the same tissues, where the size and form of structures is different. During slicing, individual optimisation of slicing angle and kind of cross-section for different kinds of tissues are the most important parts. [16]

During the histological analysis many factors have to be taken into account. The most important is the structure of cells and tissues. It provides a characteristic division between various types of organism components. Certain properties are identical for almost all types of tissues. Furthermore, the structure of a cell and its description is one of the main objectives of histology. [17]

Seventy percent of cell volume is water and chemical compounds in majority of tissues. Each cell in the body is a structurally and functionally active

unit, which can execute basic vital actions like nutrition, mechanical, chemical and physical activity and also reproduction. The most important fundamental structures are nucleus and cytoplasm. Nucleus is basophilic, which provides bonding with eosinophilic haematoxylin. On the other hand, cytoplasm is bonding with basophilic eosin, because its structure has eosinophilic properties. Cytoplasm is separated from the environment with cell membrane. Its essential compound is the cytosol, also known as matrix, in which the organelles (cytoplasmic structures) are submerged. [17]

Cell membrane separates the cell from the external environment and the organelles from cytoplasm. It divides the cytoplasm into specific areas in which different kinds of chemical processes are conducted. Cell membrane has a structure of lipid bilayer with embedded proteins. It protects the cell from its surrounding and controls the movement of cell elements and substances inside and outside the cell and its organelles. Lipids of cell membrane have two properties: the heavy hydrophobic and hydrophilic part. Hydrophilic parts of lipids are oriented outside the membrane, hydrophobic parts – inside the membrane. The cell membrane has a consistency of oil. As a liquid it flows through specific chemical bonds between hydrocarbons, but also through the presence of cholesterol, which stabilizes the structure of membrane and makes it less permeable. Lipids are constantly changing their localisation in the membrane in a very short period of time. At the same time, they rarely move from one membrane to another, which has to be catalysed by specific enzymes. Cell membrane proteins have different functions that are very important for cell metabolism. Proteins can build a receptor, which can bond with signalling molecules, like hormones. Proteins can also be used as membrane proteins. Then, they form scenic Casals in the membrane structure, which connects the outside of the cell with its inside environment. Canals provide the possibility of transport of substances. Furthermore, proteins can have enzymatic activity, which makes them a catalyst of chemical conversions. Cell membranes delimit the outer boundaries of cell organelle, such as liposomes, ribosomes, endoplasmic reticulum, nuclei. They are involved in a variety of cell processes which include ion conductivity, cell adhesion, cell signalling, but also the surface of attachment for different extracellular and intracellular structures, which can bond and interact with a cell and its elements.

Cytosol is a liquid filling the inside of cells. It is the environment for most of the cell chemical reactions. It takes about 55% of cell volume and includes hundreds of enzymes which are responsible for cell metabolism regulation.

Ribosomes are structures responsible for the synthesis of protein. They absorb basophilic dyes. Cytoplasm with big amounts of ribosomes after the

H&E dyeing has a blue colour. Ribosomes are multi-enzymatic complexes, which consist of two subunits.

Endoplasmic reticulum (ER) is another organelle surrounded by cell membrane. It takes approximately 10% of cell volume and includes containers and sacs which are connected by tubes and follicles. There are two kinds of reticulum: smooth and rough. The smooth endoplasmic reticulum lacks ribosomes. At the same time, it takes part in lipid metabolism. The smooth ER is important structure for steroid hormones production and processes of detoxification. The rough ER is studded with ribosomes responsible for protein synthesis.[18]

In the cell, other structure can also be recognised. A valuable example could be nuclei, which contains the genetic information in form of DNA, which is characteristic for eukaryotes. Cell nucleus is also protected by cell membrane. Golgi apparatus is connecting lysosomal, secretory and endocytic pathways. Mitochondria serve as a major site of energy production through a variety of enzymes. They have their own genome (mitochondria DNA) and their amount per cell depends on type and activity of specific cells. These and other organelles are characteristic for eukaryotic cells. Their structure and characteristic properties provide important factors for adjustment of dyeing and tagging techniques, which must be used during the analysis of certain types of tissues. [19]

Cells build tissues, which are divided into four basic types specific for animals. They are called muscle tissue, nervous tissue, connective tissue and epithelial tissue. Muscle tissue composes muscles in an animal body. Nervous tissue is the main component of nervous system: the central nervous system – brain and spinal cord and peripheral nervous system – branching peripheral nerves. A connective tissue is found everywhere in the body, because its main role is to connect other elements and to enable cell-to-cell and tissue-to-tissue communication. Last but not least, epithelial tissue makes the surface of organs and blood vessels.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest